

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Hideo Kojima (I)

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Good day, readers. After some time away from CoolJapan.es due to other commitments, but continuing my research for my thesis, I decided to return not only to news pieces but also to write articles about the great Japanese creatives. All of them are part of the video game industry, and the first I will discuss is Hideo Kojima, the creator of characters such as Solid Snake and Revolver Ocelot. This article will be divided into parts to avoid becoming overly lengthy. Here is the first part.

Although the Japanese were not the originators of video games as such, nor particularly involved in their early development, they became largely responsible for reshaping and revitalising the industry following the 1982 crisis that hit the Western market—especially the U.S. console sector. As I mentioned in my lecture on 5 December at the Mangafest in Seville on the importance of Japanese companies such as Nintendo in the resurgence of video games as an emerging industry and something beyond mere toys, one cannot discuss the world of video games as we know it without citing Japanese figures like Shigeru Miyamoto, Eiji Aonuma, Koji Igarashi, Tomonobu Itagaki, Masahiro Itō, or Hideo Kojima himself, among others. Many brilliant minds have contributed to the revival of this field since the 1980s, securing video games a place among cultural productions as more than simple entertainment.

Due to the temporal proximity to my article on the Super Mario Bros. series, recently published on CoolJapan.es, and taking advantage of Kojima's notoriety—especially in 2016, following his controversial departure from Konami and the re-establishment of his own studio, Kojima Productions, now independent—I chose to focus first on the Tokyo-born Hideo Kojima, leaving Mr. Miyamoto for later. I have previously discussed Shigeru Miyamoto in articles on Nintendo and Mario, as well as in my academic work, including my doctoral thesis.

To me, Hideo Kojima is one of those figures who attract either excessive criticism or undue adoration from gaming enthusiasts—often judged superficially based on his career or personality without fully appreciating his work. For instance, very few people in Spain are aware of Kojima’s work beyond the Metal Gear series and doubt his ability to innovate, despite ample evidence to the contrary—especially in recent years, as head of Kojima Productions. Here, I will focus on the person, but mainly to guide the reader, as the truly important aspect is his contribution to the video game medium.

I will attempt to move beyond the fan-centric perspective with which many media outlets approach famous game designers or directors/producers, which often biases and weakens the commentary.

Of course, I will mention the Metal Gear series, but I will not provide an exhaustive account, as that would require multiple articles; instead, I will highlight the most significant aspects of each title. Additionally, I will explore key elements of the narrative and background of each game to help understand their importance and their connections to other arts, such as cinema.

Childhood and Youth: A True Lone Wolf

Born in Tokyo’s most populous ward, Setagaya, in 1963, Kojima experienced a childhood marked by frequent changes in routine and a family situation that forced him to become self-reliant at an unusually early age. At just three years old, his parents moved for the first time—to Shirasaki, and later to Kawanishi, Kōbe, for work reasons—and it would not be the last. Additionally, his father passed away when Hideo was only thirteen.

Ironically, this situation contributed to the development of the director we know today. It fostered his early interest in film and television, as his parents’ absence left him alone at home. Kojima became fascinated with cinema from an early age, even developing a dependence on television as a companion during his solitude. Today, he admits to immediately turning on the TV when arriving at a hotel or when alone, to avoid the loneliness he felt when his family was not around when he was younger. This audiovisual passion would inevitably influence his creations, as we shall see.

However, young Kojima was not exclusively tied to Japanese media. He has stated that among his favourite television content were numerous foreign productions, including American cinema of the 1980s. This is crucial to understanding Hideo, as he is an entrepreneur who believes video games can be entirely unique in Japan, but that their enrichment comes from blending Eastern and Western influences.

Hideo Kojima in 1983, during his High School years

Hideo Kojima always wanted to work in the field of art, but partly due to the Japanese mindset of the time—that it was preferable to seek “safer” and better-paid jobs, more stable ones—and also because of the difficult situation his uncle faced when he too tried to pursue art, combined with his family’s financial struggles following his father’s death, young Hideo’s artistic ambitions were not warmly received. Consequently, he ended up dedicating his academic career to studying Economics.

Despite this, he devoted himself to writing stories for publication in magazines—often far exceeding the usual 100-page limit, sometimes reaching around 400 pages. However, he did not find much success. During this period, he met a friend who owned an old eight-millimetre camera and began to lean towards cinema. He also played in a music band as a hobby, but never succeeded in making his peers understand his desire to become a film director or writer.

This situation persisted after finishing secondary school. Most of his friends had ended up in bands or working in jobs such as insurance brokers. His own family doubted that anyone would support his pursuit of an artistic career, yet he remained determined.

We remain in the 1980s. Hideo Kojima studied Economics at the University of Tokyo.

During his free time, he developed a growing interest in playing video games on his Nintendo Famicom, gaining increasing admiration for creative minds such as Shigeru Miyamoto—*Super Mario Bros.*, *The Legend of Zelda*—and Yūji Horii—*Portopia Renzoku Satsujin Jiken*, *Dragon Quest*—and their works.

It was during his fourth year at university that he finally decided to focus his efforts on the world of video games, announcing his intentions to his classmates and friends.

Konami would become the company closely linked to almost his entire professional career as a game designer, director, and producer. His classmates and friends warned him about the instability and lack of security in a job at a video game company—in the 1980s, these were still considered minor entertainment, nothing of lasting significance—but years later, they congratulated him for persevering.

However, Kojima mentions that there was one figure who supported him from the start: his mother. According to him, she was a key figure who gave him the strength to pursue his ideas.

Kojima's early work at Konami

Kojima always wanted to work for Nintendo and was initially dissatisfied with his position as an assistant designer at Konami. Yet, not everything was unpleasant at the company, which hired him in 1986. There, he learned the fundamentals that he would later apply to his own projects within the company. Even after securing his position, his friends still doubted the reliability of this type of employment.

Kojima once attended a wedding where a friend entrusted him with the honour of delivering a celebratory speech during the very week he joined the company. When his friend introduced him, he said: “Here is Hideo Kojima, a man of great talent, who will waste it all at Konami.” Ironically, this would be the company to profit from his work thirty-five years later—and eventually dismiss him. But let's not get ahead of ourselves.

Kojima's first assignment was to contribute new ideas for the development of a company title for the MSX computer. This was *Penguin Adventure*, a sequel to *Antarctic Adventure* from 1983. The soundtrack of the first game included a classical piece by Émile Waldteufel, *Les Patineurs* (The Skaters), which you can enjoy in this orchestral version.

Title screen of *Penguin Adventure*, running on the MSX. Japanese version of the game.

The game centred on a penguin named Penta, who had to race while avoiding seals, holes in the ice, and other obstacles. For the sequel, the aforementioned *Penguin Adventure* —夢大陸アドベンチャー (*Yume Tairiku Adobenchā*, or “Adventure on the Dream Continent”) — Kojima suggested the team the creation of an entirely original soundtrack, with distinct tracks for each level. In *Antarctic Adventure*, all levels were virtually identical, merely changing the placement of obstacles, while the music remained the same for every stage. This task was handled by Yoshinori Sasaki and Kenichi Matsubara.

Here, Kojima acted only as a design assistant, supporting Ryōhei Shogaki, yet most of his ideas were adopted by the development team, resulting in a sequel that was far more polished and original than the first. The game also featured a notable graphical improvement over its predecessor and became one of the best adventure games on the MSX, later ported to systems such as the Master System and even PC.

Unfortunately, it did not enjoy the same widespread distribution as the original, which appeared on many more devices.

Kojima began experimenting with ideas that would become his trademark, such as incorporating cinematic cutscenes —presenting events to the player instead of throwing them straight into obstacle courses— and embedding a narrative into the game, rather than producing a standard arcade title that offered nothing beyond the gameplay itself. This early touch of cinematic flair would become a hallmark of his work.

Instead of a single repetitive level, players faced varied environments and challenges, from outer space to deserts. The game also allowed upgrades to the protagonist’s equipment. It included multiple endings —some unlockable, such as the “good” ending, which required pausing the game once, and if the player reached Game Over, the pauses would gradually increase by four each time: five times, nine, thirteen, and so on— along with shortcuts, secret levels, new types of enemies and obstacles, including end-of-level bosses, adding variety and replayability, which would become a signature element of Kojima’s design many years later.

Kojima grew to enjoy his work, though initially he almost quit the company. He approached his tasks obsessively, often forgetting to use the toilet for hours, sleeping very little or not at all for days, and even dreaming about ideas for the game. His colleagues advised him to take a more balanced approach, and one of his superiors approached him, expressing a desire for a new project. Kojima’s first game was not *Metal Gear*, as many believe, but *Lost World*, which was rejected and never produced.

A company executive offered him the chance to develop an action title, but due to technical limitations, the project gradually shifted into a game focused on evading enemies. It was then that Kojima conceived the idea that would eventually become the first stealth game in history as we know them: *Metal Gear*.

On the left, the cover of the original *Metal Gear* from 1987 for the MSX2, and on the right, Michael Biehn as Kyle Reese in *The Terminator* —the 1984 film directed by James Cameron. As we shall see, Hideo Kojima and his team's homages to cinema would become a constant throughout their work.

Building on the premise of characters having to escape and hide from their enemies, inspired by the films *The Great Escape* (1963) and *The Guns of Navarone* (1961), Kojima envisioned a video game in which the player would constantly need to evade foes, making direct action a secondary element. He also thought it would feel more realistic, as contemporary games of the time tended to feature nearly invincible characters capable of single-handedly destroying entire armies if necessary.

Solid Snake, the protagonist of *Metal Gear*, would have to make use of his surroundings and study enemy patrols to evade them without triggering alarms. Kojima continued his approach of incorporating scenes that told the story of the game and its characters, with numerous conversations and interactions with both secondary characters and adversaries.

The game also reflects something very typical of the modern Japanese citizen: a deep aversion to war and nuclear weapons. Hideo himself recalls the stories his father told him, having lived through the panic following the American bombings of Japan. Hence, the ultimate adversary in *Metal Gear* games is always the Metal Gear itself, in one form or another: a bipedal tank capable of launching nuclear missiles from almost anywhere.

The game's innovative gameplay premise stood out in an era when military-themed games revolved around a single soldier annihilating almost everything on-screen, surrounded by hundreds of enemies—a concept that captivated future fans of the saga. Nintendo produced a version for the Famicom and NES in 1987, which reached Europe in 1989. This followed the success of the first MSX2 release, prompting them to create their own version primarily for European and North American markets, taking advantage of the positive reception of Snake's initial adventure on the MSX2.

However, Nintendo did not involve Kojima and made severe changes unacceptable to the author, which altered the game's essence—for instance, removing a confrontation with Metal Gear itself and introducing translation errors that distorted the original story.

Solid Snake facing Metal Gear TX-55, the final boss of 1987's *Metal Gear*

Hideo Kojima's next project for Konami was *Snatcher*, a 1988 graphic adventure game released for the MSX2 and NEC's PC-8800. He drew inspiration from films such as Ridley Scott's *Blade Runner* (1982), James Cameron's *The Terminator* (1984), and Walter Hill's *Streets of Fire* (also 1984), as well as the OVA series *Bubblegum Crisis*—created in 1987 by Katsuhito Akiyama, Masami Ōbari, and Hiroaki Gōda.

The game follows an amnesiac detective named Gillian Seed, who becomes embroiled in investigating a series of cases in which strange androids murder humans and replace them. From *Blade Runner*, Kojima borrowed many visual elements, such as the protagonist's appearance and the concept of the snatchers—paralleling *Blade Runner*'s replicants.

From *The Terminator*, he took design aspects for certain elements, including the snatchers without their human disguises. Meanwhile, *Streets of Fire* and *Bubblegum Crisis* influenced the visual style as well; in *Bubblegum Crisis*, we also see androids resembling humans, alongside design elements that would inspire *Snatcher*.

It was one of the first graphic adventure games to present a mature tone and theme, featuring a deeply engaging narrative for the player. There is a nod to *Metal Gear*, as the protagonist's assistant robot bears that name—the Metal Gear Mark II. The game achieved notable success, allowing it to be released across multiple gaming systems.

Front cover of *Snatcher* for the PlayStation, released in 1996. This version was never released outside Japan and was not published in any language other than Japanese.

Unfortunately, *Snatcher* did not leave Japan until 1994, when Sega decided to localise it into English for its Sega Mega-CD version—an accessory for the Sega Mega Drive, known as the Sega Genesis in the United States—even adding audio tracks that included a reasonably good English voice dub.

In the video I link here you can enjoy gameplay of *Snatcher* on the Sega Mega-CD in proper English, and at the 13-minute mark you can even see the Metal Gear used by Gillian, with the musical theme from that video game playing as it appears. Its cyberpunk aesthetic stood out, combining the graphic adventure format —where the player solves riddles and puzzles through interaction with the environment, characters, and so on— with elements of the interactive film genre, though without overusing this approach as many other titles of the time would.

It is considered a cult video game, since despite being released on several consoles; it never received sufficient publicity and remains fairly unknown among more casual players. After the Sega CD release, later versions —for PlayStation and Sega Saturn— once again remained confined to the Japanese market.

Major studios such as Bethesda Softworks have paid homage to this video game in their own titles. In *Fallout 3* (2007), for instance, players can encounter a corpse that references one appearing in *Snatcher* —that of Jean-Jack Gibson— even carrying exactly the same items in its pockets as the original character.

This reference is not the only one. *Snatcher* was also one of the first video games to feature a combat system in which the action paused so that the player could select specific body parts to target during a shooting sequence —something later seen in *Vagrant Story* (2000), or in *Fallout 3* itself through its Vault-Tec Assisted Targeting System, or V.A.T.S. A later role-playing game by Nippon Ichi Software, *Last Rebellion* (2010), also applies this technique to its turn-based combat system.

Left —Top: Rutger Hauer as Roy Batty in *Blade Runner*. Bottom left: Harrison Ford as Rick Deckard in *Blade Runner*. Bottom right: Sting as Feyd-Rautha Harkonnen in *Dune* (1984), directed by David Lynch. Right: Screenshot from *Snatcher*. Gillian Seed can be seen on the left and Random Hajile on the right. At the lower right, in the centre, stands the Metal Gear MK II, which is also visible in the centre of the right-hand image, inside the room partially visible in the background.

A relatively loyal and consistent fan community did exist, and one enthusiast even managed to convert the classic for the infamous Virtual Boy by Nintendo —a device I already discussed in my articles on Super Mario and Nintendo video game consoles. *Snatcher* also received a Radio Drama adaptation —a very popular type of programme in Japan in which various voice actors recreate scenes from a video game or other audiovisual media such as films through music and sound effects, or alternatively expand an existing narrative with new plot elements.

The project was overseen by Shūyō Murata, an expert in the field who, before becoming a video game designer, began his career as a director of this type of audio drama series in Japan. Murata would later become the writer of several video games, including *Metal Gear Solid: Peace Walker*, *Metal Gear Solid 4: Guns of the Patriots*—for which he also served as co-director alongside Hideo Kojima— and *Metal Gear Solid V: Ground Zeroes*.

In this production, Kojima —acting as producer— also collaborated with Akira Yamaoka, composer of the Silent Hill series. This already hints at Kojima’s interest in that particular franchise, as will be discussed later. The production also featured the talent of Akio Ōtsuka —the official Japanese voice of Solid Snake— who voiced Gibson, a character appearing in the original video game, as mentioned previously.

In 1990, Kojima was also responsible for an adaptation of the original instalment in the form of a role-playing game (RPG), entitled *SD Snatcher*. This version presented a different visual style, transforming the appearance of the original title into the Super Deformed aesthetic —characters with oversized heads and a more childlike appearance— except for the game’s final scene. The title was released exclusively in Japan for the MSX2.

Kojima’s work in the 1990s

Following the success of the first *Metal Gear* and the potential the concept had demonstrated, Konami later decided to offer Nintendo the production of a second instalment without any involvement from Kojima himself, although some members of his team did participate. A new studio composed of Konami staff was formed for this purpose: Ultra Games, in an attempt by the company to improve both sales and its relationship with the American market.

The result was *Metal Gear 2: Snake's Revenge*, released in 1990. The game featured rather questionable narrative elements, such as the revelation that Big Boss —the enemy controlling the fortress into which Snake infiltrates— remained alive in the form of a cyborg. This particular decision did not please Kojima very much, although he would later revisit aspects of the idea.

Kojima first learned about the project through one of the team members during a chance encounter on a train journey. Hideo even considered developing the sequel himself —his superiors eventually asked him to create what would become the true sequel to the original *Metal Gear*. Nevertheless, he was reportedly quite surprised to discover that he actually liked the game, and only a few months after the NES version’s release he launched his own canonical sequel for the MSX2.

This sequel was titled *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake*. With it, Kojima sought to place a much stronger emphasis on storytelling within the video game medium, an approach he had begun to master through his previous experience with *Snatcher*. For this instalment, Kojima’s team also managed to incorporate a cinematic introductory sequence, similar to the one previously implemented in *Snatcher*.

Although Kojima was not the first developer to introduce cinematic scenes in an action video game, this approach would soon become a hallmark of his studio. The increasingly cinematic treatment of narrative in his games—first explored in *Penguin Adventure* and refined in *Snatcher*—would become progressively more evident in his later works.

Original MSX2 cover of *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake* (1990), alongside the original artwork by Yoshiyuki Takani used for that cover. This already illustrates Hideo Kojima's appreciation for artists of this kind, as will become evident later with Takani's subsequent collaborations with him, as well as with the inclusion of the late Noriyoshi Ōrai—who passed away in 2015—in later projects.

In other words, the introduction presented the player with sequential images resembling those of an animated series or a film, complete with opening credits, additional text, and accompanying music. The aim was to immerse the player in the situation and help establish the game's atmosphere, deliberately imitating the style of television series or action cinema of the period. The narrative was far more developed than that of most action video games of the time, including that of the original *Metal Gear*. There was greater interaction with secondary characters, and the plot addressed complex themes such as the proliferation of nuclear weapons, the existence of private military forces, and the underlying reasons why human beings so frequently find themselves at war with one another. Once again, Kojima demonstrated how a genre could be revitalised by incorporating elements from very different ones, successfully blending them into a coherent whole.

The title also introduced fully playable innovations, such as the ability for Snake to crawl along the ground while advancing through the environment—something that had already appeared in *Snake's Revenge*.

The most significant improvements in this instalment, however, produced rewarding challenges for the player and came in the form of the enemies' artificial intelligence. Whereas enemy guards had previously been limited to seeing only in straight lines — left, right, up, or down— they now became considerably more difficult to deceive. They could see at 45-degree angles, turn their heads in order to detect the player, and even pursue Snake from one screen of the map to another, making infiltration considerably more difficult. They could also hear the player when noise was produced, for instance when using a weapon without a suppressor or striking objects within the environment.

Such actions would prompt them to investigate. If the player were discovered by an enemy, an alarm indicator would appear, associated with a timer that showed the gradually reduced level of alert once the guards had been evaded, eventually returning the situation to normal and ending the search. This mechanic would later reappear in the Metal Gear series beginning with *Metal Gear Solid* and in subsequent instalments.

Interaction with non-hostile characters was also expanded. The player could be penalised, for example, if a child were injured during the mission —a detail that Kojima would revisit many years later in *Metal Gear Solid V: Ground Zeroes* (2014) and *Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain* (2015).

Snake is equipped with a radar system that allows the player to see both enemy positions and Snake's own location. However, this device ceases to function while the game is in alert mode. Progress through the story also requires the player to solve various puzzles —for instance, for unlocking some of Snake's radio frequencies— as well as making use of specific items in order to advance further.

Solid Snake crawling to avoid detection in *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake*

The game also featured a diverse range of enemy bosses with extraordinary abilities—ninjas, ex-Spetsnaz, etc. Snake would have to confront his former comrade Gray Fox, a character who would gain even greater significance in future entries. From this point onward, the Metal Gear series consistently employed this type of level boss, enriched with the narrative background Kojima imbued, so they were not merely obstacles to progress to the next stage.

The use of the radio transceiver was also crucial in this game. In the first instalment, Snake—the player— could request advice from various characters to assist if he became stuck, usually related to the specific location Snake was in.

Inspirations for the character designs in *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake*. Aside from Einstein, it is clear that Kojima made no effort to hide his fondness for blockbuster cinema and its iconic protagonists.

In the second instalment, Kojima’s programming team went further, with characters guiding the player depending on the part of the mission being undertaken, making the experience far more believable. All these mechanics would continue to evolve in future titles, as we shall see.

After this Metal Gear, Kojima returned with an original title. This was *Policenauts*, marking the point from which all of Hideo Kojima’s games would be released on CD, and later on DVD/Blu-Ray—that is, in digital disc format. It was released in July 1994 for NEC’s PC-9821 system. The game would recall *Snatcher* in terms of gameplay genre and some mechanics.

In terms of story and presentation, players would enjoy a genuine hard science fiction thriller—a subgenre of science fiction that emphasises technological plausibility, ensuring that machinery and scientific concepts are as credible as possible, often anticipating advancements likely to exist in the future—combined with police procedural elements.

Front cover of *Policenauts* in its original 1994 release for the NEC PC-9821

In this video game, which has never officially been released outside Japan —though an unofficial English patch appeared in 2009— we play as Agent Jonathan Ingram. The game features both exploration and shooting sections —very similar to the system in *Snatcher*— as well as a deeply layered story, revealed through cinematic sequences and interactions with characters encountered along the way.

For the various versions, whether for computer or console, players could use either a mouse or light guns to properly control the aiming cursor during combat sections. These action sequences occur in real time, unlike the turn-based combat in *Snatcher*.

Ingram —voiced by Hideyuki Tanaka— is the protagonist, a member of a pioneering team of five astronaut-police officers—the so-called Original Cops —trained to serve in humanity’s first space colony, Beyond Coast, in 2013—, named after NASA’s Original Seven from the Mercury program. However, something goes wrong, and, in homage to the classic Japanese tale of Tarō Urashima (which the game references multiple times), he is suspended in space for twenty-five years in cryogenic stasis. He survives thanks to his suit’s life-support system, and when he is finally rescued, he is informed of the elapsed time.

In the original tale, dating back to the fifteenth century —though its origins trace to the eighth century in the Nara period— Tarō, a fisherman, rescues a turtle being mistreated by children and is rewarded the next day with a visit to the palace of Ryūgū-jō, the Dragon God of the Sea in Japanese mythology. The turtle transforms into the Dragon God’s daughter upon arrival. Tarō stays for three days but decides to return to the surface to visit his ailing mother. The Dragon God’s daughter gives him a box and warns him never to open it. Upon his return, what felt like three days to him has actually been three hundred years in the outside world. Devastated, he eventually opens the box, which contains all the years he missed, causing him to age instantly.

Jonathan faces a similar dilemma: the life he left behind due to his accident awaits him, complete with the problems he abandoned —and many new ones arising— upon his return. He has lost his wife, Lorraine, who presumed him dead and remarried, losing hope and ceasing to wait for him; his colleagues have moved on with their lives, as has the rest of the world.

A comparable scenario is depicted in *Interstellar*, Christopher Nolan’s 2014 science-fiction masterpiece —one of my personal favourite films, and arguably the only reason I have visited a cinema in years— where pilot Cooper, played by Matthew McConaughey, travels into space and is presumed dead during a mission that, ironically, also contributes to humanity’s space colonization, much like in *Policenauts*.

During the next three years, Ingram struggles to adapt to his new life, now working as a private detective back on Earth in Los Angeles. His ex-wife approaches him for help after her current husband disappears. Initially reluctant, Jonathan is drawn into the case when Lorraine is murdered shortly after leaving his office. Unable to catch the culprit immediately, he resolves to fulfil his ex-wife’s final wish while bringing her killer to justice.

Left: Jonathan with his ex-wife, Lorraine, moments before her death. Right: Shooting sequence from *Policenauts*.

Ingram then travels to Beyond Coast, where he reunites with his former colleague, the Los Angeles police captain and fellow Original Cop, Ed Brown. With Ed's help—and the player's—he will attempt to resolve both cases. The plot involves Beyond Coast's police chief Becker and the Tokugawa corporation, which becomes embroiled in a dark criminal conspiracy that ensnares the protagonist, ultimately causing the deaths of Lorraine, her new husband, and nearly claiming Jonathan himself.

This title is considered particularly special for Hideo Kojima, as unlike other projects he has participated in, he actively oversaw and supported every official release of *Policenauts*. References to *Policenauts* appear in *Metal Gear Solid* and subsequent titles. For instance, Jonathan's hairstyle is reused for Solid Snake, his brother Liquid, and even Naked Snake/Big Boss in his youth.

Kojima embeds nods to this game in nearly every subsequent project. Examples include the operating system used by characters in *Metal Gear Solid 2*, developed by the Tokugawa company, as well as the cybernetic ninja body used by Gray Fox, and later Raiden's prosthetic body—both displaying the company's name.

Cinematic influences remain strong: Jonathan and Ed are clearly inspired by Martin Riggs and Roger Murtaugh (Mel Gibson and Danny Glover, respectively) from the *Lethal Weapon* series of movies, which started in 1987. Jonathan reflects Riggs' appearance and some of his personality traits, while Ed echoes Murtaugh's character and demeanour.

Finally, one of Kojima's most beloved secondary characters appears: Meryl Silverburgh. In *Policenauts*, she is a police officer in FOXHOUND, preserving both her visual design—including the fox firing a gun logo, later FOXHOUND's emblem in *Metal Gear Solid*—and aspects of her personality for her future counterpart in the series.

Left: Danny Glover and Mel Gibson as Roger Murtaugh and Martin Riggs.

Right: Meryl Silverburgh, Ed Brown, Karen Hojo (top center), Anna Brown (bottom center), and Jonathan Ingram in *Policenauts*.

This video game was also a pioneer in introducing animated sequences throughout its story, and it was among the first to offer high-quality voice acting, with a large number of dialogue lines—most games that included voiceovers at the time didn't have nearly as much dubbed content as *Policenauts*.

Kojima also included an Easter egg in the 1996 PlayStation version that he would later reuse in *Metal Gear Solid*. If the player had save files from *Tokimeki Memorial* —a dating game franchise in which Hideo Kojima himself participated, along with Kōji Igarashi— the system would feature conversations referencing that game. Additionally, when loading a save, the game provided a brief summary of the story events discovered so far to refresh the player’s memory, a feature also incorporated into franchises like *Resident Evil*.

From 1997 to 1999, Kojima contributed to the *Tokimeki Memorial* franchise, enhancing replayability by offering multiple endings based on the player’s choices. In these games, the goal was to develop the protagonist’s skills to attract girls and successfully date the chosen character.

He participated in three titles: *Tokimeki Memorial Drama Series Vol. 1: Nijiuro no Seishun* (1997, PlayStation and Sega Saturn) as planner, producer, and director; *Tokimeki Memorial Drama Series Vol. 2: Irodori no Love Song* (1998, PlayStation and Sega Saturn) as planner and producer; and *Tokimeki Memorial Drama Series Vol. 3: Tabidachi no Uta* (1999, PlayStation and Sega Saturn) as executive director. These games leaned more heavily into visual novel mechanics, placing greater emphasis on narrative development.

1998: *Metal Gear Solid* — International Recognition

Considered a masterpiece and one of the greatest video games in history, this title changed everything for Hideo Kojima, as well as for me and countless other players.

It was the first true stealth game of its type presented in full 3D —polygon-based, not stereoscopic— that achieved such an impact; it was also the first *Metal Gear* to receive this treatment, and the first to be fully voice-acted, line by line and scene by scene. This was Kojima’s lesson that video games could aspire to be more than mere toys for children or casual gamers.

Hideo Kojima would add something he deeply loved: cinematic artistry. In film, we experience the vision of a director and engage through watching and listening. In video games, we can go further: we participate in the experience and become the true protagonists of the story the team presents.

Front and back covers of *Metal Gear Solid* (1998) for PlayStation, PAL European version. The back cover shows the codec number —used in the codec conversation between Meryl and Snake, visible in the last in-game screenshot featured on the cover. Kojima breaks the fourth wall with the player by revealing to the player that this code is printed on the back of the game’s box.

Released in 1998 for the PlayStation, *Metal Gear Solid* retained the quality of its original Japanese voice acting through the English version and, remarkably, into Spanish —the only title in the franchise officially dubbed in Spanish. Voices like Akio Ōtsuka —Solid Snake, and the regular Japanese voice of Mel Gibson, among over 150 other roles— remain unforgettable, with Ōtsuka reprising Snake, Naked Snake, and Solidus Snake in later entries.

The English dub is also iconic, particularly David Hayter as Solid Snake, whose gravelly voice would evolve alongside the character throughout the series. Hayter was later replaced in the English dub of *Metal Gear Solid V: Ground Zeroes* and *Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain* by Kiefer Sutherland, a change lamented by fans but handled with skill by the newcomer.

In Spain, the game featured what is widely considered one of the best Spanish dubs in video game history, second only to the original *Warcraft III – Reign of Chaos* (2002). Produced at IRONIC Producciones in Barcelona, it included Alfonso Vallés as Solid Snake (also Radamanthys in *Saint Seiya* and Juba in *Gladiator*), Riki Coello as Liquid Snake (Batō in *Ghost in the Shell: Stand Alone Complex* and Hades in *Saint Seiya*), Ana María Camps as Meryl Silverburgh (Kei Amemiya in *Jin-Roh*), and Vicente Gil as Colonel Roy Campbell (Merle Dixon in *The Walking Dead*, Yoren and Craster in *Game of Thrones*, and multiple roles in *The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim*).

Kojima also introduced a novelty in this entry: the mission briefing could be fully viewed by the player, presented with animated illustrations by Yōji Shinkawa —his first major work for the franchise and my personal favourite alongside Akihiko Yoshida and Yoshitaka Amano. Shinkawa would become the conceptual artist for all characters and mechanical elements in Kojima’s games from this point onward, accompanying him during the transition from Konami to Kojima Productions. He established a mature, dynamic visual style with bold lines, interactive colour planes, and distinctive design flourishes —effectively pioneering the assignment of a dedicated artist to a video game franchise, much like Yoshitaka Amano did for Final Fantasy.

Shinkawa joined Konami in 1994 and immediately formed a close creative partnership with Kojima, driven by their shared fascination with robots —a collaboration that continues to the present day.

Yōji Shinkawa drawing Snake at an exhibition of his illustrations, held at Konami's headquarters in 2011

With *Metal Gear Solid*, Kojima managed to elevate a video game to the level of cinema, and even beyond. The integration of its 3D graphics engine, along with real-time camera use, and the aforementioned voice acting, helped the franchise convey the story and the characters' emotions with unprecedented verisimilitude.

One notable aspect of this game is that, at a time when video games often relied on pre-rendered cutscenes, *Metal Gear Solid* chose to present all sequences running in real-time within the game engine itself, maintaining cohesion and avoiding the illusion of graphics that the game hardware could not actually render.

The narrative once again tackled themes such as the proliferation of nuclear weapons and the consequences of war, while introducing the ethical dilemma of genetic manipulation. Snake's adversaries were a militant group seeking Big Boss's —his father and enemy in the previous two instalments— genes to create an army of genetically enhanced soldiers. This theme resonated with contemporary debates on cloning, such as the widely publicised Dolly the sheep experiment. Issues of cloning and genetic manipulation would continue throughout the Metal Gear series, along with Liquid Snake's intense hatred of Solid for supposedly being "Big Boss's chosen one."

The plot revolves around Liquid Snake taking up arms against the United States government to claim Big Boss's remains —considered "the perfect soldier"— to exploit his DNA. Liquid's private army, the Genome Soldiers, employed genetic engineering in a manner reminiscent of the U.S. government's fictional use of Captain America's enhancements in the 1940s comic series.

This title presents an ensemble of memorable characters who became deeply beloved by audiences, beginning with Solid Snake himself, forcibly brought back from retirement and from his hobby as a musher—a dog-sled racer—. The saga’s protagonist ceases to be merely a soldier under the player’s control and develops into a far richer character, thanks to the extensive background that Hideo Kojima and his team would gradually build throughout the *Metal Gear* franchise.

Among these figures are Roy Campbell; Hal Emmerich—better known as Otacon—, a character conceived by Kojima partly as a tribute to fans of Japanese anime and manga, and who functions narratively as a bridge between the player and Snake, reflecting how an enthusiastic fan might react when meeting their hero; and Gray Fox, who returns in the form of a cyborg ninja—initially as an enemy, but ultimately sacrificing his life to aid Snake, an act of loyalty and camaraderie that left a strong impression on the franchise’s enthusiasts.

Snake’s enemies were equally memorable, including the primary antagonist Liquid Snake, Solid’s twin brother. Characters such as Revolver Ocelot, Vulcan Raven, and Psycho Mantis earned acclaim and affection from players for their design, charisma, and iconic boss battles.

The death of *Sniper Wolf*. The elite sniper and enemy of *Solid Snake* provides one of the most memorable moments in video game history, with their sniper rifle duel set in a snow-covered landscape. Her death also becomes an emotional moment for the player, making a secondary antagonist and her motivations genuinely matter.

Kojima would continue to break the fourth wall, most notably during the confrontation with Psycho Mantis. In this encounter, the enemy speaks directly to the player, with pre-recorded lines depending on which game save files are stored on the PlayStation Memory Card. He also comments on the player’s habits, remarking whether they save their game too frequently—or, conversely, whether they risk losing progress by saving too rarely. There are other moments addressing the player directly, such as the already mentioned instruction to check the back of the game case for Meryl’s codec number; or the scene in which Ocelot tortures Snake—stating that, in order to survive the interrogation, the player must repeatedly press the circle button, and that he will notice if the controller’s turbo function is used.

The ending of the game depends on whether the player saves Meryl or Hal Emmerich, Otacon. The canonical outcome, as later entries confirm, is that Snake escapes and manages to save both characters. In subsequent instalments we see how Meryl develops a relationship of admiration and affection towards Snake, which eventually falters once she comes to know the man behind the legend; and how Otacon becomes Snake's closest friend, alongside Colonel Campbell. Emmerich ultimately becomes a crucial ally in Snake's missions and remains by his side until the end, as later events will show. Colonel Roy Campbell, who had also met Snake's father —Naked Snake/Big Boss— in the past, places his trust in him and later entrusts him once again with an immense burden in the form of a new mission.

With *Metal Gear Solid*, Kojima once again demonstrated that video games, as a synthesis of multiple artistic forms, can aspire not only to emulate cinema but even to surpass it. Unlike film, where the audience remains a spectator, here the player becomes the true protagonist of the story.

Both Solid Snake and the player are confronted with a narrative that transcends the immediate events of the game itself, forming part of a broader meta-narrative that would unfold throughout later entries in the *Metal Gear* series. The villains would continue to surprise players again and again across the franchise, and their motivations would gradually inspire a degree of respect —causing both Snake and the player to question their own assumptions.

Promotional image for *Snatcher*, by Gōichi Suda —Suda51—

Without further ado, I bid you farewell until the next entry. Thank you for your time!

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** *Metal Gear Solid: El Legado de Big Boss*, Metal Gear Informer, Konami, IGN | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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